

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF FOREIGN LINTERS

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Abstract. In foreign-made linter machines, due to the small cross-sectional area and volume of the working chamber, the seed roll forms at the required density, and with an increase in roll speed, the discharge of seeds from the chamber accelerates. However, the high rotational speed of the saw cylinder and the agitator causes seed damage and higher fiber contamination, which in turn reduces the quality of both seeds and lint. In terms of efficiency of foreign linters, research was conducted on the **MR-160-11C** linter, manufactured in the People's Republic of China and operated at the Bakht Cotton Cleaning Plant in the Syrdarya region. The results showed that the cross-sectional area of the working chamber of this linter is **22% smaller** than that of the local **5LP** linter. As a result, the seed roll rotated evenly along the length of the chamber without clogging, and the discharge of linters from the chamber accelerated.

However, when an average of **2.0% fiber** was stripped from the seed surface, the linter's productivity averaged **560 kg/h for seeds** and **29.2 kg/h for fiber**, which is **63% lower for seeds** and **17% lower for fiber** compared to the rated performance specified in the machine passport. The average seed damage rate was **5.4%**, which is **1.1 (abs.)% higher** than the requirements set by the **UCT 97-2022 technological regulation** for seed preparation. This indicates that such linters are not suitable for processing planting seeds. The average staple length of the produced lint was **5/6 mm**, while contamination averaged **8.6%**, classifying it under **Grade "B", Type "Contaminated"** according to the technical requirements of **O'zDst 660:2011 "Cotton Lint"**.

Keywords: linter, working chamber, agitator, saw cylinder, cotton raw material, fiber, cottonseed, productivity, quality indicators.

Introduction. In foreign countries, the processes of primary processing for both seed and industrial cotton are carried out within the technological systems of cotton ginning plants. According to this technological system, after ginning the seed and industrial cotton, seed cottonseeds and industrial cottonseeds are produced, respectively. The produced seed and industrial cottonseeds contain lint with an average staple length of 16 mm [1]. In foreign countries, primarily delinted seeds are planted. Therefore, seeds with this level of fuzziness are first delinted, then treated with chemicals, and prepared for sowing. In foreign countries, seed cottonseeds produced from the ginning of seed cotton are not processed through linters. The delinting process for seed cottonseeds is conducted at chemical plants. In this chemical method, the lint on the surface is delinted by burning it off with special preparations, after which the seeds are sorted, chemically treated, and prepared for sowing. In foreign countries, only industrial cottonseeds produced from the ginning of high- and low-grade industrial cotton are processed using linters. In these countries, linters are not utilized within cotton ginning plants.

Instead, linters are operated in oil and fat plants or in specialized facilities dedicated to delinting industrial cottonseeds [2]. The process of scraping lint off the cottonseed surface in these linters is performed similarly to that of local 5LP linters. Structurally, they are similar to 5LP linters, but differences exist in their feeders, working chambers, and lint separation components [3]. For instance, the feeder operates in a semi-automatic mode and lacks a section for cleaning the seeds from impurities. Consequently, the seeds are not cleaned prior to the linting process, which leads to an increase in lint impurity and elevates dust levels in the workshop air. The cross-sectional area of the working chamber is smaller than that of local linters. Due to this design, the required density of the cottonseed roll inside the working chamber is maintained, and the rotation of the roll is enhanced. As a result, blockages in the working chamber are significantly reduced, which positively impacts the linter's productivity through uninterrupted, steady operation. The productivity of foreign linters depends on the number of saws on the linter shaft, with 160 to 210 saws being used per shaft. In this case, the outer diameter of the saws can range from 320 mm to 406 mm. During the linting process, the lint scraped from the cottonseed surface is separated using either air flow or a brush drum [4, 5].

By 1970, with the aim of improving seed and lint quality while increasing linter productivity and reducing power consumption during the linting of seed and industrial cottonseeds, the Model 630 linter machines manufactured by the US company "Moss Gordin" were installed in the cottonseed linting technological line of the "Pakhtaorol" cotton ginning plant in our Republic. According to its technical specifications, the linter's saw cylinder consisted of 176 saws with an outer diameter of 320 mm and 175 inter-saw spacers. The linter working chamber featured an agitator with an outer diameter of 120 mm and a rotational speed of 525 rpm. The speed of the saw cylinder was 695 rpm, receiving its motion from an electric motor via a belt drive. During the linting process, the lint scraped from the seed surface by the cylinder saws was separated from the saw teeth using a brush drum [6]. To prevent excessive roll density and to avoid roll stoppage during the cottonseed linting process, a small-volume working chamber was utilized (Figure 1).

Research conducted on the operational performance of the linter indicated that when scraping an average of 1.5% of lint from the seed surface, the seed processing capacity did not exceed an average of 600 kg/h, and the lint yield did not exceed an average of 18 kg/h. It was determined that when scraping an average of 2.0% of lint from the seed surface, the linter's seed processing productivity decreased, not exceeding an average of 400 kg/h.

The damage rate of the seeds processed by this linter was high, leading to the conclusion that seed cottonseeds could not be linted using such machines. Furthermore, due to the absence of a seed cleaning system in the linter feeder, the lint produced from the cottonseed linting process had a high level of contamination. Because of these deficiencies, these linters were subsequently replaced with local PMP-160 models.

Materials and Methods. In 2010, linters manufactured by the Turkish company "Adamak" were installed at the oil and fat plant of "Tola Textile" LLC in the Namangan region to increase linter productivity, reduce the number of linters in the technological line, and improve product quality

According to the linter's construction, the outer diameter of the saw cylinder shaft is 200 mm, onto which 199 saws with an outer diameter of 406 mm and 198 inter-saw spacers are assembled. The rotational speed of the saw cylinder is 830 rpm [7-8]. During the linting process, the lint scraped from the seed surface is separated from the saw teeth of the cylinder using a

brush drum rotating at 1000 rpm. The cross-sectional area of the linter's working chamber has been reduced by an average of 22% compared to that of the local 5LP linter. In production research, when scraping an average of 2.2% of lint from the seed surface, the linter's seed processing productivity per single saw averaged 5.0 kg/h, while the lint yield averaged 0.18 kg/h. The damage rate of the processed seeds was high, averaging 6.3%. The mass fraction of trash impurities and whole seeds in the lint reached 8.9%. Due to the high content of short fibers (staple length less than 5 mm) and fuzz in the lint produced from linting Grade I industrial cottonseeds, it was classified as Type "B", "Dirty" class according to the state standard O'zDst 660:2011 "Cotton Lint - Technical Specifications" [7].

In our country, scraping lint from the surface of seed and industrial cottonseeds is primarily carried out using 5LP model linter machines. In foreign countries, cottonseeds produced from the ginning of seed cotton are not processed through linters; the lint on their surface is removed using chemical methods.

Industrial cottonseeds produced from the ginning of industrial cotton are directed to the linting process. This linting process is not conducted within cotton ginning plants. Instead, the linting of industrial cottonseeds is performed at oil and fat plants or specialized facilities dedicated to processing industrial cottonseeds. In these facilities, the linting process is carried out using linter equipment that is structurally similar to local linters.

Today, certain cotton ginning plants in our Republic primarily utilize foreign-manufactured linter equipment to process industrial cottonseeds.

To study the efficiency of linters manufactured in foreign countries and utilized in local cotton ginning plants, as well as their impact on the quality and quantity of the produced seed and lint, experimental research was conducted on the linters installed in the cottonseed linting workshop of the "Bakht" cotton ginning plant in the Sirdaryo region. The cottonseed linting workshop of the enterprise is equipped with MR-160-11C model linters manufactured by the Chinese company "Swan" ("Lebed") [9]. The general view of the MR-160-11C linter is presented in Figure 3. According to the construction of the linter equipment, it consists of feed rollers (1), a chute (2), a working chamber (3), an agitator (4), a cottonseed comb (5), a saw cylinder (6), a grate (7), a trash (mote) catcher (8), a brush drum (9), and a lint conveying duct (10). The working chamber of the linter consists of a breastshield/apron (1), an agitator (2), a shaft (3), a cottonseed comb (4), a grate screen (5), a saw cylinder (6),

1- feed roller, 2- working chamber, 3- agitator, 4- cottonseed comb, 5- grate screen, 6- saw cylinder, 7- trash (mote) auger, 8- lint conveying duct.

Schematic diagram of the MR-160-11C linter manufactured in China.

inter-saw spacers (7), and a density valve (8).

The diameter of the agitator shaft (3) is 45 mm, and the outer diameter of the agitator, including the edges of the blades, is 150 mm. The number of grates in the grate screen is 161, the number of saws on the saw cylinder is 160, and the number of inter-saw spacers is 159 [10]. The cross-sectional area of the linter's working chamber has been reduced by an average of 24% compared to that of the local 5LP linter. The rotational speed of the saw cylinder in the linter is 1100 rpm, and the speed of the agitator is 700 rpm. During the cottonseed linting process, the lint scraped from the seed surface is separated from the saw teeth of the cylinder using air flow and is transported through the lint conveying duct to the lint condenser [11, 12]. During the research period, samples were taken and analyzed in the enterprise laboratory to determine the fuzziness and damage rate of the cottonseeds fed into and discharged from the linter, the composition of the produced seeds by fuzziness, the linter's processing productivity in terms of seed and lint, and the mass fraction of trash impurities and whole seeds in the lint.

Results and Discussion. The experimental work was conducted using Grade I, Class 2 industrial cotton of the "Sulton" variety, which had an average initial moisture content of 11.4% and a trash content of 9.3% [13, 14]. In this process, the industrial cottonseeds produced from the enterprise's 8DP-90 model gin had a moisture content of 9.3% and a fuzziness level of 10.5%. Cottonseeds with this moisture and fuzziness profile were processed using the MR-160-11C model linter. The experiments were carried out using new saws with an outer diameter of 320 mm that had been operated for 4 hours.

The cottonseed linting process was performed in accordance with the PDI70-2017 Coordinated Technology for Primary Cotton Processing [15]. Consequently, cottonseeds with an average fuzziness level of 7.5% were produced during the linting process. The average damage rate of the produced seeds was 5.4%, which is 1.1% (abs.) higher than the limit set for cottonseed damage from linter equipment in the UChT 97-2022 Technological Regulation for Seed Cottonseed Preparation. Due to the high damage rate of the produced industrial cottonseeds, it was concluded that seed cottonseeds cannot be processed using this type of linter [16].

Conclusion. Due to the small cross-sectional area and volume of the working chamber of the linters manufactured by the Turkish company "Adamak" and utilized at the "Tola Textile" LLC oil and fat plant in the Namangan region, the cottonseed roll in the working chamber achieved the required density. The resulting increase in the roll's rotational speed accelerated the discharge of seeds from the chamber. However, due to the high rotational speeds of the saw cylinder and the agitator, cottonseed damage increased, along with the mass fraction of trash impurities and whole seeds in the lint, ultimately leading to a decline in both cottonseed and lint quality.

The results of the research conducted on the MR-160-11C model linter, manufactured by the "Swan" ("Lebed") company of the People's Republic of China and utilized at the "Bakht" cotton ginning plant in the Sirdaryo region, revealed that because the cross-sectional area of the linter's working chamber is 22% smaller than that of the local 5LP linter, the cottonseed roll rotated uniformly along the length of the chamber without clogging. Consequently, an acceleration in the discharge of linted seeds from the working chamber was observed. However, when scraping an average of 2.0% of lint from the seed surface, the linter's seed processing productivity averaged 560 kg/h, and the lint yield averaged 29.2 kg/h. This

indicates that the throughput was 63% lower for seeds and 17% lower for lint compared to the linter's nominal passport capacity. The average damage rate of the produced seeds was 5.4%, which is 1.1% (abs.) higher than the limit established for cottonseed damage from linter equipment in the UChT 97-2022 Technological Regulation for Seed Cottonseed Preparation, confirming that seed cottonseeds cannot be processed using these linters. The produced lint had an average staple length of 5/6 mm and an average contamination level of 8.6%, classifying it as Type "B", "Dirty" class according to the O'zDst 660:2011 "Cotton Lint - Technical Specifications" state standard.

The optimal size of the cross-sectional area and volume of the working chambers in foreign linters ensured the required density of the cottonseed roll. The subsequent increase in roll speed accelerated the discharge of linted seeds from the chamber, positively impacting linter productivity. However, the high rotational speed of the saw cylinders and agitators in these linters caused an increase in cottonseed damage and lint contamination, resulting in a degradation of both seed and lint quality.

By studying the advantages of the working chambers in foreign linters, it was concluded that the working chamber of the local 5LP linter needs to be modernized and optimized. This improvement is necessary to increase productivity, enhance the quality of produced seeds and lint, and reduce electricity and spare parts consumption during the linting of both industrial and seed cottonseeds.

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